

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: COLE****FIRST NAME: MARK****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following best describes the phases of academic essay writing?
- Only preliminary research and final proofreading are essential; drafting is optional if the writer is experienced.
 - The essay writing process is strictly sequential and linear, with each stage taking approximately equal time, starting with research, followed by drafting, and concluding with finalizing.
 - Preliminary, drafting, and finalizing are the key phases, though they are not always strictly sequential, and their duration/importance may vary.¹**
 - The only phase necessary for successful essay writing is the drafting phase; preliminary and finalizing stages can be skipped if the writer is experienced.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7–17.

2. What is the key difference between scholarly academic writing and all other forms of writing?
- The critical importance of research and references which allows the global community of scholars to access, check, and repurpose each other's scholarship.²**
 - The use of the English language.
 - The universal reliance on the Chicago Manual of Style for uniform formatting, style, and presentation.
 - The necessity for academic essays to be engaging and interesting.
3. Which of the following best describes the philosophy of Kate L. Turabian's *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*?
- The Turabian is primarily a strict set of rules and regulations for academic writing.
 - The Turabian views academic writing as a transactional process focused solely on the end result of publication.
 - The Turabian is a living testimony to the principles of rigor, clarity, consistency, and structure, essential for the development and preservation of human knowledge.³**
 - The Turabian emphasizes the use of specialized vocabulary and complex sentence structures to demonstrate scholarly competence.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 12.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 134–35.

4. Which of the following is NOT a characteristic of effective research as defined in Part I of the Turabian?
- Effective research is a structured, compelling, and mutually respectful dialogue with readers.
 - The goal of research is to provide definitive and permanent answers to research questions.**⁴
 - Research involves the systematic search for credible and authoritative sources while avoiding dubious ones.
 - Effective research is characterized by formulating clear questions, defining the problem to be solved, and proposing solutions.
5. What distinguishes the Notes-Bibliography Style for citations from the Author-Date Style for citations?
- The Notes-Bibliography Style is suited for humanities, allowing for extensive commentary, and is less concerned with the publication date, unlike the Author-Date Style, which is used in sciences where the timeliness of research is crucial.**⁵
 - The Notes-Bibliography Style emphasizes the author's first name in citations, while the Author-Date Style focuses on the last name.

⁴ Turabian, 134–35.

⁵ Turabian, 223.

- The Notes-Bibliography Style is preferred for its brevity and precision in scientific disciplines, whereas the Author-Date Style is favored in the humanities for its detailed commentary on sources.
 - The Notes-Bibliography Style relies solely on in-text citations, while the Author-Date Style utilizes footnotes and endnotes for source documentation.
6. What is a key formatting distinction between notes and bibliographies in the Notes-Bibliography Style as highlighted in the Turabian?
- In notes, a semicolon separates components of an entry, whereas in bibliography entries, a colon is used.
 - Bibliographies require the inclusion of the publication medium, while notes do not.
 - In notes, the author's name is presented first name followed by the last name, but in a bibliography, the order is reversed, with the last name followed by the first name.**⁶
 - Notes use italicized titles for sources, whereas bibliography entries use quotation marks.
7. According to James P. Sampson's *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, which of the following best describes the stages or the interconnected components of dissertation research?
- Introduction, Literature Review, Data Collection, Analysis, and Conclusion.

⁶ Turabian, 156.

- The Concept or Pre-Prospectus Paper, the Prospectus, the Dissertation, and the Dissertation Manuscript.**⁷
- Abstract, Methodology, Results, Discussion, and References.
- Hypothesis, Experimental Design, Data Gathering, Data Analysis, and Implications.
8. According to Sampson's *Guide*, which of the following are crucial for dissertation research success?
- Extensive funding and access to advanced research facilities.
- Collaboration, strategic planning, and ongoing communication.**⁸
- Publication in high-impact journals during the research phase.
- Focus on solitary work to ensure originality and avoid bias.
9. According to the 2021 *English Style Guide* by the European Commission, what is the primary purpose of establishing linguistic conventions for writing and translations within the EU?
- To enforce strict adherence to British English grammar and spelling across all EU documents.
- To prioritize the use of legal jargon in all EU communications to maintain technical accuracy.

⁷ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 7–17.

⁸ Sampson, 10–15.

- To discourage the use of English by non-native speakers within the European Commission.
- To promote clarity in communication, given the important subject matters and the complex and multilingual environment of the EU.⁹**

10. How does the EU's *English Style Guide* recommend adapting language styles for different contexts?

- It suggests using complex and technical language for all types of documents to ensure precision.
- It advocates for the exclusive use of American English to standardize documents across the EU.
- It recommends using colloquial and idiomatic expressions to make texts more engaging for a wide audience.
- It emphasizes clear, straightforward, non-colloquial British English, tailoring language styles to the document's context, like using simple language for web content and precise terminology for legal documents.¹⁰**

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Brussels: The European Commission, 2021), 4.

¹⁰ European Commission, 4–5.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Commission. *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. Brussels: The European Commission, 2021.

Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.